

**Invited
speaker**

Fame: 2

**Upgrade
Funding
company**

You can get 1
patent (Fame 3) for
each pair of non-
shared projects

**Upgrade
Big research
group**

You can publish
2 papers in your
non-shared projects

**Invited
speaker**

Fame: 2

**Upgrade
Funding
company**

You can get 1
patent (Fame 3) for
each pair of non-
shared projects

**Upgrade
Big research
group**

You can publish
2 papers in your
non-shared projects

**Invited
speaker**

Fame: 2

**Upgrade
Funding
company**

You can get 1
patent (Fame 3) for
each pair of non-
shared projects

**Upgrade
Big research
group**

You can publish
2 papers in your
non-shared projects